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A Purview of Preaching and Teaching of Jesus Christ on Prayer, Forgiveness and Violence

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Abstract

The overview of the teaching of Jesus Christ during His earthly ministry is a focus that cannot be trivialized in the practice of Christianity as a whole. This is because, the teaching of Jesus Christ is the bedrock on which principles, doctrines, and practices of the Christian faith are based and as a result, a consideration and reiteration of the major teachings of Jesus Christ is important to emphasize the expectation of Jesus Christ from His disciples and by extension to the contemporary Christians. This paper therefore examines some of the major teachings of Christ as discovered through the content of the Gospel, which contains the earthly preaching and teaching of Jesus Christ and as such, didactics are deduced and to be understood and inculcated by contemporary Christians. It is, therefore, recommended that if these teachings of Jesus Christ on love, forgiveness, and violence are followed religiously, there will likely be a peaceful society devoid of hatred, conflict, and violence. This will likely aid in the achievement of Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with peaceful society by 2030.

Keywords: Forgiveness, Goal 16 of the SDGs, Prayer, Preaching of Jesus Christ, Teaching of Jesus Christ, Violence

Introduction

A cursory look in the study of world religions and religious leaders has obviously distinguished Jesus Christ, the lead figure for Christianity as a distinct personality with his mode and content of teachings. His miracles were great; His teachings were even greater. The things Jesus taught are more important than his methods. "He gave man a completely new way of life which is summed up in what has been called the golden rule of the Bible" (Kuo, 2002: 45): "Therefore, whatever you want men to do to you do also to them, for this is the Law and the Prophets" (Matthew 7:12). Therefore, "the golden rule is far above any other way of life" (Kuo, 2002: 45). The essence of the teachings of Jesus is in the Sermon on the Mount found in Matthew 5, 6, and 7. The sermon does not have a connected thought but is made up of sayings on different subjects. It begins with a group of "beatitudes" in which blessing is pronounced upon those who please God. For example, "Blessed are the merciful, for they shall obtain mercy. Blessed is the pure in heart, for they shall see God" (Matthew 5:7, 8).

One will note that Jesus gives His blessing, not to the rich or famous, but to those whose hearts are right and who strive to serve God by serving other people. In fact, He also said in one of His teachings, "Do not lay up for yourselves treasures on earth, where moth and rust destroy and where thieves break in and steal; but lay up for yourselves treasures in heaven..." (Matthew 6:19, 20), the Lord shows that true riches are to be found in spiritual, not material things. Therefore, this paper shall consider some of the teachings of Jesus to see their significance, especially in the peaceful coexistence of people in society.

Jesus, the Good Teacher

It is impossible to read the Gospels without getting a sense of the intensity and passion of Jesus' teachings. He spoke with great authority on spiritual matters, "often leaving his detractors tongue-tied and looking foolish" (Michael, 1996: 335). It means many of His teachings are disturbing and shake one out of comfort and contentment. He spoke of loving God above all other things, caring about all other people as much as we care about ourselves, the coming kingdom of God, and eternal life. Furthermore, Jesus Christ often spoke in parables, using common images of nature and agriculture, to deliver His spiritual messages. Many people, often including His disciples, were left baffled by the parables. But one about Him that is paramount is that He explained His parables to his disciples in private, but many of the explanations have not been recorded in the Gospels. With many similar parables, Jesus Christ spoke the word to them, as much as they could understand. He did not say anything to them without using a parable. But when he was alone with his own disciples, he explained everything (Mark 4:33-34).

The reason people do find it difficult to understand His parables is that, Jesus has also said it in His word that, "The secret of the kingdom of God has been given to you. But to those on the outside everything is said in parables so that, they may be ever seeing but never perceiving, and ever hearing but never understanding; otherwise, they might turn and be forgiven" (Mark 4:10-12). Therefore, with this statement of Jesus, one could draw out that Jesus constructed His parables so that only those who were pure of heart and receptive to His teachings could understand them. On the contrary, "Jesus' enemies and the merely curious were left baffled" (Flowers, 2001: 465). This 'harsh' attitude of Jesus may be the way of making His message available and inviting those who wish to understand and believe while never forcing anyone to know and accept His truths. Marshall (1997: 869) says, "If Jesus had spoken in plain language, the sheer power of His personality and message might have forced many to believe, even against their own will. By speaking in parables, Jesus made it possible to decline the invitation to understanding and commitment found in the parables."

The question one often asks about Jesus' parables is how can you explain to someone an experience they have never had? And how would you explain the beauty of a sunset to someone who had never seen one? The answer to this question is not far-fetched. Coleman (1990: 362) says, "Parables are skillfully painted mental pictures to help one to understand the kingdom of God and other spiritual things one has never experienced." This means that "the parables of Jesus are the appropriate form of communication for bringing to men the message of the kingdom, since their function is to shake them into seeing things in a new way" (Coleman, 1990: 362). These parables are a means of enlightenment and persuasion, intended to bring the hearers to the point

of decision. Jesus, as it were, stands where his hearers stand, and uses imagery familiar to them to bring new and unfamiliar insights to them.

Some Selected Teachings of Jesus

In one of the synoptic gospels, Jesus says, "Do not think that I have come to abolish the Law or the Prophets; I have not come to abolish them, but to fulfill them" (Matthew 5:17). In this passage, which is part of the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus said that he didn't intend to abolish the old Jewish religious laws, such as the Ten Commandments and the various regulations on marriage, inheritance, property rights, diet, and similar matters. However, "he often did re-interpret these laws, or add to them, sometimes in very radical ways. As a result of this, it makes some of his teachings very controversial" (Hanna, 2002: 687). Moreover, even today, some of his teachings still seem very radical to many people. Here are some of the best-known examples:

Teaching On Violence

As Jesus Christ said on the mountain, "You have heard that it was said, 'eye for eye, and tooth for tooth.' But I tell you, do not resist an evil person. If someone strikes you on the right cheek, turn to him the other also." (Matthew 5:38-39). Looking at the world today, some Christians try to strictly adhere to this principle of non-resistance. Some of them have been put in prison, or even executed, for refusing to participate in wars. In Matthew 5:44 Jesus says "Love your enemies." Some people interpret this to mean that "you should try to help them rather than harm them" (Hanna, 2002: 687). Others also will say that "any needed punishments should be left to God" (Hanna, 2002: 687). However, there are many modern Christians who consider these ideas to be unrealistic. They believe that it is sometimes necessary to defend oneself or even to launch the initial attack. Many people also believe that evil-doers must be punished for their crimes, or at least locked up to prevent them from doing further harm.

Teaching On Wealth

In Mark 10:25, Jesus says, "It is easier for a camel to go through the eye of a needle than for a rich man to enter the Kingdom of God." Some scholars think that the word "camel" in this statement resulted from an accidental mis-copying of a very similar word which meant rope. Thus, Jesus may have actually said "It is easier for a rope to go through the eye of a needle..." (Hauge, 1995: 223) which is a more natural metaphor. Another tradition traces the "eye of a needle" as referring to the alternative route for a camel to pass through when it arrives late in the night and the big gate of the city has been locked. This is because, the alternate route is narrowly created and the camel must be willing and ready to surrender himself for pushing to enter through the narrow gate made through the fence (Buetel, n.d.). But whether he said camel or rope, his point was that it is very hard for a rich person to go to heaven. In fact, Mark 10:17-22 indicates that the only way a rich person can go to heaven is, in Jesus' words, to "sell everything you have and give to the poor." Some people try to avoid this conclusion by pointing to Mark 10:27, which says, "All things are possible with God". However, "God can make it possible for a rich man to go to heaven" (Buetel, n.d.). Certainly, this is true, but the context of the statement indicates that "God would

accomplish this by inspiring the rich man to reform his life and willingly give his money to the poor" (Lucas, 1995: 456).

Jesus Christ also warned against the accumulation of wealth on several other occasions. In Matthew 6:19, He says, "Do not store up for yourselves treasures on earth", and a few verses later, in Matthew 6:24, he says "You cannot serve both God and Money". In Luke 6:24 he says "Woe to you who are rich." Jesus disapproved of wealth accumulation because he thought it was wrong for some people to live in wasteful luxury while others starved. According to the Book of Acts, his original followers tried to live by these teachings after he left them. They formed a community in Jerusalem, known as the Nazarenes, in which everyone "had everything in common" (Acts 2:44), and any new member had to sell his or her possessions and give the proceeds to a common fund. However, many modern Christians disagree with these ideas. They see nothing wrong with acquiring money and wealth. People who do become wealthy are often admired by others.

Teaching on Compassion and Forgiveness

The teachings quoted above are examples of what is sometimes called the Difficult Teachings of Jesus because most people find them very hard to follow. "Their radical nature has led some people to call Jesus an extreme moralist. Others have called Him a utopian dreamer, a social or political reformer, or even a communist" (Amy, 2002: 115). However, whatever else He was, He was also a person of great compassion. He had very strong feelings for the poor, the downtrodden, the outcasts, and the persecuted, and he was keenly aware of the oppression and injustice that kept them in their place. This is why he condemned greedy people who live in opulence while so many others suffer in poverty. More so, Jesus also had a very strong willingness to forgive. He believed that everyone deserves another chance. A good example of this is his teaching about turning the other cheek: "Not only should you instantly forgive a man who strikes you on one cheek, but you should also turn your other cheek to give him a chance to see his error and realize the need to reform him" (Scolt, 1971: 445). From this point of view, one may draw that Jesus probably didn't mean it literally when he talked about gouging out eyes and cutting off hands. Most likely he was simply using hyperbole to emphasize his point. But the mere fact that he could talk in this way provides another example of just how strong his convictions were. Of course, most people can feel compassion, and most people have some willingness to forgive. Only few, if any, have ever felt these emotions as deeply as Jesus did, or had as strong convictions as he did. That difference may explain why some of his teachings seem so radical to us.

Teaching On Prayer

Prayer is a means of communication with God. Jesus' teaching on prayer was focused on training His disciples how to talk to God. One day Jesus was praying in a certain place. When he finished, one of his disciples said to him, Lord, teach us to pray, just as John taught his disciples. According to John Kant who made this assertion that,

It is therefore fitting to pray to the Father, to call upon him with all our mind, with all our will, not externally with the lips, but inwardly with the mind as it is drawn up from below, sighing, repenting for our unrighteousness, for the life we have been living, confessing

our sins, perceiving the empty deceptions we have been living, weeping over how we have found ourselves in the darkness of ignorance, mourning for ourselves and asking the Father to have pity on us; hating ourselves for what we have become. For as Jesus says in Matthew 5:4, 6 "Blessed are they that mourn; for they shall be comforted (Kant, 1962: 114).

Blessed are they which do hunger and thirst after righteousness; for they shall be filled, Then Jesus says in Luke 14:26, "If any man come to me, and hate not his father, and mother, and wife, and children, and brethren, and sisters, yea, and his own life, he cannot be my disciple." In other words, you cannot serve God and mammon. The connection to the father is within, "mind connects with Mind" (Kant, 1962: 114). This is our father; approach him as a little child would approach his father for help. It's our child-like faith in our Father's ability to make us whole again that opens our understanding of the teachings of Jesus. No man can open the door to understanding, only the father can do this. "Seek; Knock; Ask!" If you understand these teachings and do them. Your sins are forgiven, go and sin no more.

Furthermore, Jesus says; "When you pray, pray in private where no one can see you. Prayer is between you and your father. Do not use vain repetition. Do not ask for earthly things, for your father knows what things you need before you ask. While the soul can justify our thoughts, words, and deeds through rationalization, the Father cannot be deceived" (Matthew 6:5-8; Luke 16:15). Jesus Christ gives us an example of prayer in Matthew 6:9-13: this should be a prayer guide, an example of praying, not to become a "vain repetition" to be recited in public "with bowed heads." Jesus always raised his head, like a little child standing before his father and looking upwards, "Father be merciful to me a sinner." (Luke 18:13). Agahel (1998: 117) says,

Forgive others of their trespasses against you, forgive those who hate you, forgive those who use you, forgive those who steal from you, forgive those who hurt you, and so on. Do not return evil for evil; for if you do, what better are you than they? Whatsoever another does against you, remember Jesus words in Luke 2:34, "Father, forgive them, for they know not what they do.

God the Father is Spirit (Mind), and they that worship him must worship him in Spirit (Mind) and in truth (John 4:24). When you have lifted your mind, from being connected to the Soul below, and connect with the Father above, then shall you begin to experience revelation, the truth that shall eventually set you free from the Soul and this evil world.

The Teaching of Jesus About the Kingdom of God

The Kingdom of God is the place where Jesus is King. It is a spiritual, invisible kingdom that has made its presence felt to a degree in the affairs of this earth, but only to a limited extent. It is not confined to a particular geographical location, nor a particular religious organization. The Kingdom is truly present in a place to the extent Christ is honored as Lord and his will is done there. There are two types of kingdoms taught by Jesus, the kingdom of God and the kingdom of Satan. Firstly, some biblical scholars view the Kingdom of God as an alternative term for 'heaven', but Jesus taught that it could be in our midst on earth, and come to us now through his ministry – for example – the ministry of casting out demons by the Spirit of God (Matthew 12:28). When Jesus spoke of entering the Kingdom he was not merely saying 'going to heaven when you die'.

He was talking about entering into the Kingdom life here and now. This includes heaven later on, and whatever plans God may have for us on the new earth, but it is far more than that. The Kingdom of Heaven is not about 'pie in the sky when you die'

The second kingdom is the kingdom of Satan which stands as an opposing kingdom to the kingdom of God. Jesus spoke of Satan's kingdom (Matthew 12:26). The Scripture declares that 'the whole world lies under the sway of the evil one' (1 John 5:19). Satan is called 'the god of this age' (2 Corinthians 4:4), 'the prince of the power of the air' and 'the spirit who now works in the sons of disobedience' (Ephesians 2:2). "Satan, operating through a vast hierarchical network of fallen angels, evil spirits or demons as they are variously known, exercises a stupendous influence on the hearts and lives of men, women, boys and girls" (Borrel, 2004: 56). This means that the existence of Satan's kingdom accounts for the hatred, the wars, the stupidity and selfishness of mankind, the existence of false religions and philosophies and the presence of every kind of perversion and deception on the face of the earth. Satanic influence is very effective because it operates in the background, and is generally not openly displayed. It is almost always covered under another name or philosophy. The kingdom of God is in perpetual conflict with the spiritual kingdom of Satan. These are the two spiritual kingdoms that dominate the affairs of mankind and influence the lives of multitudes. They are totally opposite in nature. There is no third kingdom. The kingdom of God only advances through the destruction of the works and influence of the devil.

Furthermore, in Jesus Christ's earthly ministry, Jesus taught much about the kingdom of God. Many of His parables compared the kingdom of God to such familiar things as leaven or mustard seed. Daniel had prophesied that "God would establish an indestructible kingdom" (Daniel 2:44). What the Jews were looking for was a temporal kingdom, "but the kingdom Christ came to establish was a spiritual one" (Borrel, 2004: 56). He was to reign, not on the throne of David in Jerusalem, but in the hearts of men. Jesus did not teach that He would ever establish an earthly kingdom, but He did teach that His kingdom was the church (Matthew 16:18, 19) and that it soon was to be established.

Jesus Teaching on Love

Love is many things in our culture. For many it can be likened to an electric charge: either the zap of the feeling is there or it is not. For others, love is an arrangement, almost like a contract, sometimes voluntary, other times it is imposed by circumstances. Love for family members is not a given ordinance; instead, events have necessitated it. Marriages often proceed with this kind of arranged love. As long as the contract works and the zap is present, the arrangement is on. Often such love is managed by performance. "Love is to be demonstrated by what is done by an action: If you really cared, you would do this for someone" (Watterd, 1989: 121). This kind of love that Jesus teaches is a description of what love is for the child of God. "The love Jesus calls for is none of the things described above" (Watterd, 1989: 121). Jesus decries the contemporary culture's version of love. What is required to possess true love is an understanding of what it is to be loved by God and how God wishes one to love. At the center of Jesus' sermon "is a unique concept of love" (Tellar, 1998: 333).

In the Old Testament, as Jesus' response pertaining to the direction to love God, Jesus was referencing the first commandment, recorded in Deuteronomy 6:4-5, "Hear, O Israel: The LORD our God is one LORD: And thou shalt love the LORD thy God with all thine heart, and with all thy soul, and with all thy might". These are the words that begin the '*Shema*' which is the primary declaration of faith of every practicing Jewish person. The first part, "Hear O Israel, the Lord our God, the Lord is One", is the most famous statement of all in Judaism and it is said, is the first statement Jewish teachers instruct their students to recite. The second commandment of Jesus is based on Leviticus 19:18 "Love your fellow as yourself"; it reflects the primary striving of every Jewish person; this particular statement is said to encompass all of the Spiritual Law of Judaism. Furthermore, Jesus does not wait to make his point on the unusual character of such love. Although the righteous will be persecuted and rejected and God will judge the persecutors, Jesus issues a call to love the enemy. In fact, Jesus' call is specific: "Love your enemies, do good to those who hate you, bless those who curse you, and pray for those who mistreat you". Whether in attitude, action, word, or intercession, the enemy is to be loved. Jesus wants more than condemnation of the outside world. Jesus' call to disciples focuses not on our words to others, though John 11:37-54 does issue a stinging challenge regarding our words. Rather, Jesus zeroes in on our actions and attitudes toward others. He offers no platitudes about how outsiders should be viewed. There is no abstract call to divide one's thought by "hating the sin, but loving the sinner." True as this saying is, Jesus is concerned that we follow through on it and show our love in concrete service for the sinner. Our model is God himself: "God so loved the world that he gave his only begotten Son" (John 3:16, 36). So, Jesus Christ calls for the performance of love in action, thought, and petition.

The significance of Jesus Christ's teaching is characterized by simplicity. That is, he used words the common people could understand and took his illustrations from those things with which they were familiar. Many of his principles were set forth by parables. "A parable is a true-to-life story with a lesson" (Williams, 1997: 321). For instance, in the story of the prodigal son in Luke 15:11-32, one will see that it is a wonderful story that could have happened, Christ did not tell it just to entertain His listeners. But He intended to show that a loving God will receive again His children when they stray. The number of Christ's parables is usually placed between 27 and 50, depending on what is classified as a parable. Of these, a majority deal with human beings while the others are built around animals, plants, or other objects with which the people were familiar. It is the wish of Jesus that men come to Him. But while He will compel no man to accept Him, He invites all. "Come to me, all you who labor and are heavy laden, and I will give you rest. Take my yoke upon you and learn from me, for I am gentle and lowly in heart, and you will find rest for your souls. For My yoke is easy and my burden is light" (Matthew 11:28-30). In other words, the significance of His teaching and what He wants His followers to learn is that they should put their entire minds to Him and seek the kingdom of God first.

Conclusion

An examination of the approach of Jesus Christ to people during His earthly ministry distinguishes Him from other teachers of the law, prophets, priests, and various religious and political leaders. His teachings were based on principles that were not intended to annul the

existing law on the ground but were obviously different in approach to the existing mode of practice that is obtainable in the large society of the people. His teachings caused religious leaders to raise eyebrows since they contradicted their wrong interpretations that had been dominantly practiced of which they had selfishly benefitted in the status quo and the intended change and rectification of such anomalies did not settle well with the various leaders of the people and as such, they chose to wage war against Jesus from the beginning of his earthly ministry till the time he was crucified.

The persecutions, criticism, and opposition received by Jesus Christ from the people never made Him succumb or be mute in insisting on the validity of his teachings because, he was purposeful and He aimed at correcting the wrong that has become the norm of the days and also to make man realize that, it is possible to live like God. His teachings brought regard to human understanding of the mind of God and what God expects man to do by ultimately loving God and secondly loving fellow men which is the fulfillment of the entirety of the law. It is, therefore, recommended that if these teachings of Jesus Christ on love, forgiveness, and violence are followed religiously, there will likely be a peaceful society devoid of hatred, conflict, and violence. This will likely aid in the achievement of Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with peaceful society by 2030.

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